

Worst Case Heavy Ion Testing Conditions for Normally Off GaN-Based High Electron Mobility Transistor

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Abstract — Gallium Nitride (GaN) High Electron Mobility Transistors (HEMT) are promising devices in power conversion for space application because of their high efficiency, their reduced size and the natural immunity of p-GaN gate technology to Total Ionizing Dose (TID). Nevertheless, the use of power GaN HEMT in space environment shall be carefully considered with respect to heavy ion Single Event Effect (SEE). This paper presents two alternatives SEE testing conditions on GaN HEMT to investigate for worst case that are switching condition and high tilt beam condition. Test bench and sample preparation for SEE test campaign are presented and discussed. Finally, alternative testing conditions results are compared to classical SEE testing conditions and Safe Operating Area (SOA) obtained are discussed with the help of TCAD modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gallium Nitride (GaN) high electron mobility transistors are promising devices in power conversion for space application because of their high efficiency, their reduced size and the natural immunity of p-GaN gate technology to Total Ionizing Dose (TID). Nevertheless, the use of power GaN HEMT in space environment shall be carefully considered with respect to heavy ion Single Event Effect (SEE) failure for mainly two reasons. First, commercially available GaN HEMT are Commercial Off The Shelves (COTS) devices designed for automotive or industrial applications and therefore not designed to be robust to heavy ion. Second, this technology is relatively recent and subjected to continuous manufacturing and design improvements. Consequently, SEE hardness survey of GaN HEMT devices is of prime importance. This survey is usually done using the same testing conditions as the one developed and validated a long time ago for Metal Oxide Semi-conductor component (MOSFET). These testing conditions being, direction of ion beam perpendicular to die surface (also called normal incidence), MOSFET being OFF state with a V_{GS} of 0V or below (if needed to investigate over blocked condition) and component at room temperature. However, it is important to consider that power GaN HEMT and power MOSFET are

significantly different as for instance GaN HEMT power cell structure is lateral contrary to power MOSFET that has a vertical structure. This difference renders MOSFET SEE testing conditions heritage questionable for GaN HEMT especially regarding worst case testing conditions. This paper presents two alternative SEE testing conditions to investigate for the worst case. First is dynamic testing to evaluate the influence of high temperature and fast switching and second is highly tilted beam condition because it was reported in [1] to have a potential influence on SOA. Test bench and sample preparation to allow alternative testing conditions are presented and discussed. Finally, alternative testing conditions results are compared to classical SEE testing condition and Safe Operating Area (SOA) obtained are discussed with the help of TCAD modeling.

II. TEST BENCH FOR DYNAMIC SEE TESTING CONDITION

A. Presentation of the test bench

A specific test bench was developed for the SEE robustness evaluation of GaN HEMT, in hard-switching conditions or in DC polarization, while deporting the power Device Under Test (DUT) during irradiation. This deported configuration allows only the DUT to be inside the irradiation chamber, while the test setup (equipment and driver) were outside. The test setup is based on a gate driver board that switch the DUT using a resistive load, and implements characterization tools in order to extract health indicators during the SEE test in DC polarization (I_{GSS}/I_{DSS} , V_{TH} ...). A switching matrix is used to switch the DUT from hard-switching operation to DC polarization (Fig. 1). Only the GaN power device to be evaluated is placed in a vacuum chamber, about 2.5 meters away from the gate driver board. This configuration allows a more versatile operation of the test bench. The main problematic of this test configuration is to perform switching operation of the DUT while placed at a significant distance, due to all the parasitic elements of the test setup itself (cable length, interfaces with vacuum chamber, etc.). This involves operating limitations, such as high R_L value

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to limit current $I_{DS} < 1$ A, to avoid strong overvoltage due to stray inductance and/or damaging the device. A 50Ω resistor at the output of the power source is used for the impedance adaptation. It minimizes signal reflections in the transmission lines and therefore the disruption of the operation of the DUT.

Fig. 1 : Test bench schematic

This bench is fully instrumented and controlled by a Python program that manages all the instrumentation of the various equipment.

B. Example of switching waveform

Fig. 2 exposes an example of waveforms extracted on a GaN HEMT (GS66516T) during multi-pulse switching operation. The V_{driver} signal (yellow) is measured on the gate driver. The V_G signal is measured on the vacuum chamber interface, and allow observing the signal integrity on the DUT. Very low voltage ripples are observed. The signal V_D (red) is the drain to source voltage V_{DS} also measured at the chamber interface. Finally, the signal I_{total} is the current I_{DS} and is measured using a Hall Effect current probe.

Fig. 2 : Example of waveforms extracted on GaN HEMT GS66516T

Even with the important distance between the test bench and the DUT, the waveforms are clean, and do not present any critical oscillation during the operation of the device. Only the turn-off V_{DS} signal is slow (around $1\mu s$) compared to a typical application case. This is due to the stray capacitance of the test setup (mainly the long-sized cables), which need to be charged with limited I_{DS} current.

C. Thermal evaluation under vacuum

The importance of the switching losses due to the test setup implies a significant heating of the DUT. During the first validation tests performed in air, temperatures above $100^\circ C$

were easily reached in switching operation. The irradiation test campaign being carried out in a vacuum chamber, an even higher temperature is reached due to lack of heat dissipation by convection and may induce device failure. In order to evaluate device temperature during the tests inside the vacuum chamber, and identify operating limits, temperature sensors (RTD Pt1000) were placed on the backside of the DUT Printed Circuit Board (PCB) and directly on device as closed as possible to active region (on thermal pad for GaN Systems or on substrate for EPC references) and compared with temperature measured on backside. Preliminary validation tests were performed as a function of device operating conditions in a vacuum chamber. Results obtained on GaN System component tested at 100kHz under 400V and 400mA are exposed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 : Temperature evolution over operating time in switching conditions 400 V - 400 mA - 100 kHz.

The red curve is the temperature evolution measured directly on the thermal pad of the device GS66516T, the yellow curve is the temperature measured on the backside of the PCB. During SEE tests, only device's temperature, measured on the backside of the DUT PCB will be possible. Therefore, these preliminary tests allowed us evaluating the difference between device temperature and PCB backside temperature in order to limit device temperature during SEE test to $150^\circ C$ maximum to ensure safe operation.

III. REFERENCES SELECTION

References from EPC, GaN Systems and Panasonic were selected for the study. Justifications for this selection are given below. The highest voltage EPC references available at that time were selected because it has been observed in [2-3] that high voltage GaN components were more sensitive to SEE compare to low voltage references. Two different generations of components were selected, EPC2010C, which is from the fourth generation of component (Gen 4) and the oldest available at that time and EPC2215, (Gen 6), the latest generation available at that time. Both components are rated at 200V but have different specific On-state resistance respectively $104 m\Omega \cdot mm^2$ and $44 m\Omega \cdot mm^2$. The specific On-state resistance is given by the product between On-state resistance and die surface. This difference indicates that the distance between drain and source interdigital fingers of the GaN HEMT structure were reduced and consequently that electric field at OFF-state is increased. It is therefore expected to observe an

evolution of the safe operating area as a function of component generation. For comparison purposes, lower voltage references were also selected: EPC2104 and EPC2102, respectively rated at 100V and 60V both being Gen 5. The GaN Systems reference chosen was GS66516T. It is a 650V rated component with a thermal pad on top side of the package. This configuration was preferred to bottom cooled because it is easier to prepare for SEE test campaign. The 650V rated component has been preferred to a 100V rated one because of its higher sensitivity to SEE. It was foreseen initially to test CoolGaN references but due to procurement issues, because of worldwide component penury, it has been decided to use the Panasonic PGA26E19BA components in stock. This reference is now obsolete but results obtained on the PGA components should be similar to CoolGaN component as it was already observed in a previous study [2]. Nevertheless, this assumption will have to be verified in a future work.

IV. SAMPLE PREPARATION FOR SEE TEST CAMPAIGN

In order to perform SEE test in dynamic configuration components shall be mounted on (PCB) as recommended by the manufacturer in normal operating conditions. Consequently, the sample preparation method used in this paper for SEE test campaign has been developed to be compliant with normal mounting configuration of components. Detail regarding sample preparation were already presented in [3]. After component soldering on a daughter board, EPC and GaN Systems components are prepared by thinning the silicon substrate down to less than $50\mu\text{m}$ whereas Panasonic component are prepared by chemical opening of plastic package. After component preparation, a connector is soldered on daughter board backside to allow its connection on a mother board having an SMA connector to apply a V_{GS} voltage and a BNC connector to apply V_{DS} voltage. A temperature sensor is mounted on the backside of the daughter board to evaluate component junction temperature during switching test thanks to the dedicated calibration presented in paragraph II-C.

Fig. 4. Picture of EPC21010C component after preparation and mounting of a mother board.

Electrical characteristics were measured before and after every component preparation. Table I presents a summary of static electrical measurements done on EPC21010C before and after silicon substrate thinning. One can see that substrate thinning has absolutely no influence on static electrical parameters.

TABLE I
STATIC MEASUREMENTS BEFORE AND AFTER THINNING ON EPC21010C

Parameter	Unit	Before	After	Test conditions
I_{DSS}	μA	0.113	0.121	$V_{GS}=0\text{V}$, $V_{DS}=160\text{V}$
R_{DSON}	$\text{m}\Omega$	22.8	23.1	$V_{GS}=5\text{V}$, $I_{DS}=10\text{A}$
V_{SD}	V	2.45	2.413	$I_{SD}=0.5\text{A}$, $V_{GS}=0\text{V}$
V_{TH}	V	1.953	1.936	$V_{GS}=V_{DS}$, $I_{DS}=6\text{mA}$
$I_{GSS}(+)$	μA	1.942	1.978	$V_{DS}=0\text{V}$, $V_{GS}=5\text{V}$
$I_{GSS}(-)$	μA	-1.171	-1.853	$V_{DS}=0\text{V}$, $V_{GS}=-4\text{V}$

Dynamic ON-State Resistance (DyR_{DSON}) measurements were also performed to evaluate potential impact of substrate thinning. DyR_{DSON} measurement principle is to apply a V_{DS} voltage stress (80% of V_{DS} max data sheet) during 10 seconds and $1.5\ \mu\text{s}$ after releasing the stress multiple R_{DSON} measurement are performed during 15 ms. On EPC references, no variation of DyR_{DSON} after substrate thinning was observed but on GaN Systems component a significant increase was observed has shown on Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. DyR_{DSON} evolution of GS66516T after substrate thinning.

This behavior is a direct consequence of component preparation as in package structure there exist an electrical connection between substrate and source via the copper top plate on backside to prevent from DyR_{DSON} evolution. Backside side thinning process remove this connection and therefore affects DyR_{DSON} behavior. This undesirable effect has been corrected to avoid electrical failure during dynamic testing. As shown of Fig. 6 a dot of conductive glue was added on left side of the package to restore the substrate to source connection.

Fig. 6. Picture of GS66516T component after substrate thinning and substrate to source connection restored.

V. HEAVY ION BEAM SELECTION

In normal incidence condition, the range associated with ion cocktail usually available is sufficient to perform relevant SEE

test. For instance, using UCL facility it is 73 μm range for Xenon but, as shown in Table II, it is only 25 μm with 70° tilted beam condition. Such low range is clearly not compliant with sample preparation technic used on EPC and GaN Systems references because of the remaining silicon thickness on top of GaN layer and therefore only the Panasonic reference has been tested in high tilt beam configuration.

TABLE II
ION BEAM CHARACTERISTICS

Ion	Energy (MeV)	Range (μm in Si)	Tilt ($^\circ$)	Surface LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)
¹²⁴ Xe ³⁵⁺	995	73	0	62.5
¹²⁴ Xe ³⁵⁺	995	25	70	183
¹⁰³ Rh ³¹⁺	972	89	0	46
¹⁰³ Rh ³¹⁺	972	63	45	65
¹⁰³ Rh ³¹⁺	972	30	70	134

For EPC and GaN Systems, it has been decided to use the Rhodium ion because at 50 μm silicon depth the LET curve is almost constant whereas for Xenon at 50 μm silicon depth it is curve's tail where LET is decreasing quickly. The Rhodium LET plateau is illustrated in Fig. 7 where one can see that LET in sensitive volume is around 55 MeV.cm²/mg and is almost constant along 20 μm . The Rhodium LET plateau is interesting because it allows minimizing potential part-to-part SOA variability due to remaining silicon thickness differences coming from device preparation.

Fig. 7. Illustration of LET in Silicon volume in normal incidence beam condition for 3 ions at UCL.

VI. SEE RESULTS

Test campaign has been done at UCL facility using Rhodium ion, a flux of 5000 cm⁻².s⁻¹ for a total fluency of 1.10⁶ cm⁻² on each part to obtain a pass status. For each part that successfully pass a test condition the gate to source leakage and drain to source leakage were measured and parameters were still compliant with electrical specification. Results are presented and discussed below for three-test conditions.

A. Static results in normal incidence

Safe Operating Area results, obtained on components being OFF-state with a V_{GS} of 0V, are presented in table III where Pass and Fail voltages were obtained on a same part. For each tested part, the V_{DS} voltage was increased step by step up to Single Event Burn out (SEB) even if voltage applied was above Absolute Maximum Rating (AMR) of data sheet. All failures were obtained under beam ON except for EPC2104 that failed

out of beam, which is not surprising as applied voltage was twice above maximum rating. It is interesting to notice that, even when V_{DS} voltage was largely above AMR, failure was never observed immediately after beam ON but SEB was obtained for at least 10% of total fluency and sometime up to 50%. This observation tends to indicate that the sensitive volume is very small or that the ion needs to strike a cell weakest than all the others to initiate SEB.

TABLE III
STATIC SEE RESULTS SUMMARY

Part number	V _{DS} AMR (V)	Manufacturer (Generation)	Tilt angle	V Pass (V)	V Fail (V)
EPC2102	60	EPC (Gen5)	0°	100	120
EPC2104	100	EPC (Gen5)	0°	180	200
EPC2010C	200	EPC (Gen4)	0°	220	250
EPC2215	200	EPC (Gen6)	0°	150	160
GS66516T	650	GaN Systems	0°	400	425
PGA26E19BA	600	Panasonic	0°	350	400

From results in table III, it is confirmed that lowest voltage references show a very high robustness to SEE and that the 600V-650V references need to be used below 60% of their maximum voltage. Nevertheless, the latest generation of EPC 200V component starts to be sensitive when V_{DS} is just above 75% of AMR while the oldest generation is sensitive only above AMR. This behavior is a direct consequence of the higher electric field on Gen 6 devices compared to Gen4 which consequently implies a lowest margin on breakdown voltage. Indeed, destructive break down voltage measurements performed on fresh device indicates around 120V V_{BR} difference between Gen 6 and Gen 4 (Fig. 8).

$$I_{DSS} = f(V_{DS}) \text{ at } 25^\circ\text{C}$$

Fig. 8. Breakdown voltage (V_{BR}) measurements of EPC devices.

B. Dynamic results in normal incidence

Safe Operating Area results obtained in static testing condition were challenged on fresh devices when tested in dynamic condition and results are presented in table IV. During the test the switching frequency was chosen to obtain a junction temperature close to 150°C. A weak SOA decrease of 10V was observed on EPC2215 but it may be imputed to part to variability or to the negative voltage (-2V) on gate terminal during OFF state provided by gate driver characteristic which

is known to be a worst case testing condition [1]. For GS66516T a 50V higher SOA was obtained in dynamic configuration on one part. This observation was confirmed on another part where a first dynamic test was successfully conducted at 500V. Then, a second test was conducted again at 500V on the same part but in static configuration after having waited for device to cool down. Failure was observed quickly after beam ON. This increase of the SOA observed in dynamic condition may be explained by the very high temperature of GaN-AlGaIn layer (more than 150°C) induced by electrical losses. Indeed, it is well known that impact ionization and avalanche phenomena involved in SEB mechanism [4] are less efficient at high temperature. On PGA26E19BA no negative impact on SOA of dynamic test configuration was observed but test was limited to SOA obtained in static configuration to save parts for the high tilt beam tests.

TABLE IV
DYNAMIC SEE RESULTS SUMMARY

Part number	V_{GS} (V)	Frequency (kHz)	V Pass (V)	V Fail (V)
EPC2010C	-2/5	100	200	-
EPC2215	-2/5	100	-	150
PGA26E19BA	0/6	100	350	-
GS66516T (part1)	0/6	50	450	-
GS66516T (part1)	0/6	10	-	500
GS66516T (part2)	0/6	10	500	-
GS66516T (part2)	0	0	-	500

C. High tilt and roll beam results

Panasonic component PGA26E19BA have been tested by varying tilt or roll beam angle up to 70° as defined in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Definition of tilt and roll angle of incidence.

Using a tilt angle, the heavy ion track is perpendicular to interdigitated fingers structure but using a roll angle the ion track is parallel to interdigitated fingers structure. This difference as illustrated in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Illustration of ion direction with respect to interdigitate fingers structure in tilt or roll beam configuration.

SEE results obtained are presented in table V.

TABLE V
TILT AND ROLL SEE RESULTS SUMMARY

Part number	Roll angle	Tilt angle	V Pass (V)	V Fail (V)
PGA26E19BA (part 1)	0°	0°	350	-
PGA26E19BA (part 1)	0°	45°	350	-
PGA26E19BA (part 1)	0°	70°	-	350
PGA26E19BA (part 2)	70°	0°	350	-
PGA26E19BA (part 2)	0°	0°	-	400
PGA26E19BA (part 3)	0°	0°	350	-
PGA26E19BA (part 3)	0°	70°	-	350
PGA26E19BA (part 4)	0°	0°	200	-
PGA26E19BA (part 4)	0°	70°	-	200

One can see that, depending on tilt or roll test configuration, the SOA is definitely not the same. In roll configuration, that is to say when ion track is parallel to interdigitated fingers structure of the component, SOA results are equivalent to those observed in normal incidence. In tilt configuration and up to 45°, the SEE results are also equivalent to those observed in normal incidence but when angle is increased up to 70°, one can see that SOA is drastically decreased. Unfortunately, only four parts were prepared and we did not manage to obtain a pass results even for V_{DS} of 200V. It is important to mention that all failures in high tilt beam configuration were observed almost immediately after beam ON, even the last trial at 200V. Consequently, we suspect that 200V V_{DS} may still be far from SOA. Moreover, we also suspect that a higher tilt beam configuration would have continued to decrease SOA. This result shows that, when the ion track is in the direction of the electric field it is a worst case testing condition. This behavior may be explained by the higher effective LET associated with the high tilt beam as it was already observed that higher LET implies lower SOA [5].

From these SEE results obtained in high tilt beam configuration, three questions arise. What would be the SOA of PGA devices with a beam tilted almost at 90°? Would this high sensitivity be also observed with both tilt and roll beam configurations? That is to say when heavy ions strike interdigitated fingers structure between parallel and perpendicular direction. Are Panasonic GaN HEMT the only references sensitive to high tilt? This will have to be investigated more in detail in a future work

VII. TCAD MODELLING

In order to investigate the effect of the tilt incidence angle, we performed 2D TCAD simulations of heavy ion interaction with a commercial power GaN HEMT reference that has a nominal voltage of 200V. The simulated structure was extracted from physical analysis and the details of the simulation setup are presented in [6]. The simulated heavy ion has a constant LET of 5 MeV.cm²/mg and a constant track length of 2.5μm starting from the dielectric/barrier interface layer. The peak charge injection occurs at the instant $t=20$ ps. The impact position is located between the gate and the drain because it was identified as being within the most sensitive region of the device. The structure is impacted in its off-state with $V_{GS}=0V$

and $V_{ds}=200V$.

Fig. 11. Total current density (in $A.cm^{-2}$) at $t=20$ and 400 ps for an incidence angle of 0° (top) and 45° (bottom).

Fig. 11 presents 2D views of the total current density for both incidences at two instants. During the peak injection at 20 ps, the maximum current density follows the heavy ion path. At 400 ps, at normal incidence, the leakage current path below the gate is about to disappear, whereas at 45° incidence angle, it is still very present and a region of avalanche is appearing below the drain.

Fig. 12 presents the resulting drain current transients. At normal incidence (0°), we observe a small and short transient current pulse. For an angle of 45° , after a similar short current pulse, we observe an important increase due to the triggering of the avalanche phenomenon. This clearly indicates that the tilted case is the worst case for this device. This can be simply explained by the fact that the deposited charge in the layers that contribute to the charge collection is 1.4 times greater with an angle of 45° (and directed towards the drain) than at normal incidence. Indeed, as the tilt angle increases, there is more charge available for being collected by drift, which facilitates the triggering of the avalanche phenomenon, which will be at the origin of the failure [6].

Fig. 11. Drain current transients for incidence angle of 0° and 45° .

VIII. CONCLUSION

Three SEE testing conditions were evaluated to find worst case condition and the following conclusion can be proposed. Static OFF state configuration is worst compared to dynamic switch condition. This behavior may be explained by a highest temperature of GaN-AlGaN layer during dynamic test because impact ionization and avalanche phenomena involved in SEB mechanism are less efficient at high temperature. On the contrary, high tilt ion beam configuration with ion track direction perpendicular to the interdigitated fingers structure has shown to be drastically worst case compared to normal incidence for Panasonic component. This behavior may be explained by the higher effective LET associated with high tilt. This high tilt configuration will have to be investigated more in detail regarding tilt and roll angle and tested on other references.

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